
ISSN: 2456-9089

The International Journal for Indian and East Asian Studies

*A Multicultural and Multidisciplinary Semiannual
International Peer Reviewed Online Research Journal*

Volume 8

Issue I & II

(2025)

Published by
ijieas.org

CONTENTS

"IJIEAS"

➤	Gender, Survival, and the Literary Imagination of Park Kyung-ri, Park Wan-suh, and Oh Jung-hee <i>Anshuman Tomar</i>	01-16
➤	Shifting Dynamics of East Asian Soft Power in India: Korea's Ascendancy over Japan <i>Varun Tomar</i>	17-31
➤	History of English Education in Korea: A Failed Attempt? <i>Rahul Raj</i>	32-38
➤	A Study on Reunification of the Korean Peninsula: Focusing on the Perspective of Globalization <i>Mukul Anand</i>	39-49
➤	Post-Industrial Korea: Role Of State in Fostering Innovation, CCEI Initiative of Park Geun-Hye <i>Smita Deka</i>	50-63
➤	Cultural Diplomacy and Soft Power: Connecting Links between South Korea and India <i>Vijendra Kumar</i>	64-72
➤	Breaking the Political Glass Ceiling: Women's Representation in India and South Korea <i>Ankit Kumar</i>	73-84
➤	Cross-Linguistic Analysis of Morphological and Lexical Features in Korean, Hindi and English <i>Mukesh Kumar Jaiswal</i>	85-101

Cultural Diplomacy and Soft Power: Connecting Links between South Korea and India

Vijendra Kumar*

Abstract

India and South Korea share a rich cultural heritage and deep historical connections. Recently, both countries have emerged as cultural capitals in their own ways, and their soft power is significantly appreciated globally. The growing cultural proximity between the two nations has emerged as a significant factor in shaping the economic and trade relations of both countries. This paper analyses the impact of soft power and cultural power on the economic relations between the two countries. This would also highlight the significance of informal connections in establishing formal ties between India and South Korea.

Keywords: Cultural capital; Soft power; Cultural power; Cultural richness.

1. Introduction

In a rapidly growing, interconnected era, diplomacy has evolved beyond economic and trade partnerships. Soft power and cultural diplomacy have emerged as key tools for fostering cooperation and building perennial partnerships between countries. South Korea and India share a rich cultural heritage and vibrant historical identities. Over the past decades, the country's relationship has not only flourished economically but also through cultural exchanges and people-to-people connections. The global popularity of K-Pop and K-dramas has made inroads into India as well, and they are immensely appreciated and enjoyed by Indians (Kanozia & Ganghariya, 2021).

In the same way, the growing popularity of Yoga among Koreans is due to various factors, such as psychological well-being and stress management in the fast-paced Korean society (Kim & Kwon, 2025). Additionally, the natural healing process has gained prominence in Korean society, so Ayurveda is gradually becoming popular as a nature-based medicine (The Korea Herald, 2025). Therefore, cultural exchanges between the countries and their soft power have emerged as a significant area in deepening bilateral ties. The cultural exchanges have enhanced mutual understanding and opened new avenues for collaboration. Soft power is playing an essential role in bridging the South Korea-India economic and cultural divides, creating a relationship that transcends traditional diplomacy and lays the foundation for an even deeper, sustainable partnership. Over the years, both countries have seen a remarkable journey in establishing themselves as significant soft powers in the region, rooted in their rich cultural and historical heritage, shared democratic values and globally recognised entertainment industries.

* PhD Scholar, Centre for East Asian Studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University.

Although the cultural connections between the countries have not been fully acknowledged, both countries are seriously committed to engaging through soft power and shared historical heritage, which have played an essential role in strengthening bilateral ties and enhancing their presence in Southeast Asia as well.

India and South Korea relations have improved significantly over the last few decades. Initially, economic opportunities and scope were the primary drivers of improving bilateral ties between them. However, structural and strategic factors have lately emerged as significant pillars of cooperation in the security domain (Brewster, 2010). There is ample literature that analyses and comprehends the growing proximity between the countries in the economic and security domains (Panda, 2012). There is also literature on the impediments and missed opportunities in their relationship and its prospects (Mishra, 2020). However, it would be quite interesting to examine the soft power of both countries and their roles in their growing relationship. India and South Korea have sufficient soft power, even though, according to various rankings, they are not among the world's top 10 soft powers. This arguably happens because the parameters in most rankings are selected to measure soft power, not because of the limitations in the soft power of both countries (Mishra, 2023). The concept of soft power can be understood in various ways. For example, the soft power may be defined as the power of 'getting others to want the outcomes that you want' (Nye, 2008). Still, it can also be used to understand the defensive concept, which says 'able to resist demand for working in a particular way by any external player' (Yildirim & Aslan, 2020).

2. Soft Power of India

Since ancient times, India has had a great cultural and civilizational history, but Indian foreign policy has begun to articulate its position for the national interest more actively in recent years (Kugiel, 2017). The growing debates about the concept of 'soft power' have caused India to rethink its foreign policy from the perspective of its cultural richness, civilizational values, and modern political values, to complement its growing 'hard power'. Cultural richness in the forms of Indian arts, spiritualism, yoga, food, festivals, music, and various dance forms has been quite attractive and fascinating to the world for so long, but its use to reshape foreign policy in the national interest is quite contemporary. For example, Yoga has its roots in India and has gained global appreciation and popularity for a long time. However, the active role of the Government of India in promoting Yoga as a globally recognised International Yoga Day, through the United Nations, has been a phenomenon for only a decade. In recent years, India, through its embassies in other countries and other supporting bodies, has been promoting yoga for a healthy body and mind, in which a large number of people participate (Jha, 2023). There is no denying that it's a deliberate attempt by the Indian government to demonstrate India's soft power and improve India's image on the global stage (Mazumdar, 2018). The soft power of India comprises its cultural richness, civilizational values, democratic aspirations, and historical cultural connections

with other countries. Additionally, India's approach of 'unity in diversity' and '*vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*' (the world is my family) is globally appreciated, and India's peace-loving approach is immensely praiseworthy all over the world. Furthermore, India's immense cultural diversity has been a notable source of its soft power worldwide.

An American writer, Mark Twain, beautifully described India in his writings as 'India is the cradle of the human race, birthplace of human speech, mother of history, grandmother of legend and great grandmother of traditions'. Therefore, India has a unique image globally in the domains of knowledge and philosophy. India's spirituality, Yoga, Ayurveda, mathematics, and its status as the birthplace of Buddhism have all contributed significantly to India becoming the cultural capital of the world. With its unique civilisation and cultural values, India has emerged as a seat of the highest human values of love, peace, tolerance and brotherhood and the source of profound knowledge and wisdom, the Vishwaguru to the world. It is important to note that modern Western thinkers have gradually started to acknowledge the ancient Indian Knowledge. Additionally, democratic practices after independence have significantly contributed to India's soft power (Narang, 2023). The end of racial discrimination and the promotion of equality and human rights are offshoots of Indian democratic values. Furthermore, India's historic and cultural connections with other countries continue to shape India's soft power. From ancient times, through Buddhism, India's cultural richness reached many parts of the world (Sen, 2014). India's vast diaspora from the US, Canada, and the UAE to Southeast Asian countries like China, Japan, and South Korea helps bolster its soft power worldwide. The spread of Buddhism led to exchanges of monks, travellers, traders, ideas, and culture from these countries to India. At present, these connections provide essential support for India's soft power. In contemporary times, Indian music, dance, and Bollywood movies are appreciated worldwide. Indian classical music and Carnatic dance connect people around the world with India (Sen, 2014).

3. Soft Power of South Korea

South Korean soft power has gained significant prominence in the contemporary world. In recent years, Korean pop culture, movies, dramas, cuisine, and cosmetic products have gained global attention and spread rapidly worldwide. The rapid rise of Korean culture worldwide came to be known as the Korean wave, or hallyu (한류). This has created a very positive image of Korea, which appreciates both its tradition and innovation (Jung & Lee, 2010). Actually, Korean cultural entertainers have created a highly influential and reputable image of South Korea worldwide. South Korea has impressed the world with its spectacular growth and technological advancements in the first fifty years after independence, and it has emerged as a cultural power in recent decades. South Korea's cultural progress as a soft power can be explained in two phases. In the first phase of the Korean cultural wave, Korean dramas became popular in Southeast Asian countries such as China and Japan. In the second phase of the Korean cultural wave, with YouTube gaining popularity, Korean pop music reached other parts of the world (Kim Bok-rae,

2015). Similarly, the *Gangnam Style* song by Psy became so popular amongst audiences in the US, Europe, and other parts of the world. In recent times, K-Pop groups like BTS and *BLACKPINK* have reached every household and are quite popular amongst the younger generations worldwide. With the Netflix series *Squid Game* and Oscar-winning Korean movies like *Parasite* capturing the imaginations of audiences around the world, they are highly appreciated worldwide.

When BTS spoke at the United Nations General Assembly and met with then-US President Joe Biden, it was a major demonstration of South Korea's soft power. Therefore, the Korean entertainment industry has contributed significantly to establishing a powerful global image of South Korea. Further, *Hallyu* (한류) has also significantly benefited South Korea economically. According to one study, the hallyu's contribution to South Korea's GDP was US \$1.87 billion in 2004 and increased to US \$12.3 billion in 2019 (Parc, 2021). One study estimates that there are approximately 90 billion BTS fans worldwide, which is almost twice the population of South Korea. The Blackpink Instagram account has almost 370 million followers, which is quite impressive (Landsberg, 2023). Therefore, the creative economy of South Korea is booming like a rocket ship, capturing the imagination of the world.

The growing cultural power of South Korea has driven people across the world to want to know more about Korea, its history, its unique culture, and its food (Yoon, 2014). The global popularity of the Korean language has led younger generations worldwide to know Korea beyond BTS and K-dramas. They want to know about historical figures in Korea, such as Ulchi Mondok, Yi Sun-sin, the turtle-shaped ship (Kabuksan), King Sejong, pansori, samulnori, Taekwondo, and so on. The cultural power of South Korea has indeed given its image a strong boost worldwide. There has been greater interest in Korean cultural centres that cater to those seeking to learn more about Korea, its history, culture, and language. According to one study, there are a total of 33 cultural centres in 32 countries and 234 King Sejong Institutes in 82 countries (Hwang, 2023).

4. Soft Powers of India and South Korea and connecting links

Since ancient times, India and South Korea have shared a rich cultural heritage and deep historical connections. The tale of the Ayodhya princess who went to Korea and married a Korean King is quite popular in South Korea. It is one of the building blocks of India's and South Korea's flourishing relationship. According to the *Samguk Yusa*, Korea's historical account of the three kingdoms, in the 1st century AD, a princess of Ayodhya named Suriratna (Heo Hwang-ok) arrived in Korea. She married the Korean King Kim Suro of the Gaya dynasty. She brought many Indian cultural items, including a pagoda. It is said that two of her children adopted her family name, Hao, and that Koreans with the Hao surname and Kimhae Kims are said to have

family connections with India (Lee, 1993). Although the historical fact of such a story may be uncertain, it is still important because most Koreans believe it and serves as an important pillar in establishing a strong India-South Korea relationship. Several Korean movies and Korean dramas depict the story and further reinforce the connections between the two nations. Similarly, Buddhism is another important pillar in building connections between the two nations; it went to Korea via China. It was first officially introduced in the Koguryo kingdom in 372 AD during the reign of King Sosurim (Keel, 1978). Since then, Buddhism became the state religion of Korea until 1392. Actually, it became an important cultural link between India and South Korea, as several monks visited from India to South Korea and vice versa, and came to know about each other's cultures, people, economies, and other aspects.

Recently, Yoga has gained significant popularity in South Korea. According to one study, almost 14% of Koreans aged 19 to 29 had practised yoga in 2019 (Yoon, 2020). The Indian government has also tried hard to spread yoga; in 2011, an Indian cultural centre was opened in Seoul, and in 2013, another was opened in Busan, both of which promote yoga and provide training. When the United Nations declared the 21st of June as International Yoga Day, around 1,200 people performed yoga at Gwanghwamun Plaza (Dhar, 2021). Additionally, the Seoul National University of South Korea offers courses on Indian Yoga and philosophy. Similarly, Taekwondo of South Korea has become quite popular in India. Many Indian youngsters have developed an interest in learning taekwondo in recent decades. Although it has been around for many decades, it has become quite popular among younger generations and children in India in recent years (Business Standard, 2013). The cultural connections between the two nations can be measured by the rise of the Korean wave in India, and Koreans are also educating themselves about yoga and Indian philosophy. The Act East Policy of India and the New Southern Policy of South Korea have further contributed to the relationship between the two countries. Around 15,000 Koreans live in India, despite many inconveniences related to their stay, food, and working environment (Mishra, 2023). According to the Minister of External Affairs of India, 1364 Indian students are pursuing their education in Korea in 2022 (Hwang, 2023), and around 2015, Korean students were studying in India.

Tourism is another important area which promotes people-to-people connections between the two countries. People from India and South Korea have been visiting each other's tourist destinations, although the numbers are quite low. For example, 28.6 million people from South Korea travelled abroad, but only 140,000 visited India, and only 110,000 Indians visited Korea, in 2018 (Ahuja, 2019). There are several complaints from Korean tourists visiting India, for example, a lack of good infrastructure, Korean food, and safety. India's famous Buddhist pilgrimage sites, including Bodhgaya, Rajgir, Sarnath, Shravasti, and Kushinagar, also lack proper facilities that Koreans expect while visiting these places. Because of these limitations, India ranks 16th among Koreans' travel destinations, and South Korea ranks 17th among Indians' travel destinations (Ahuja, 2019). India's Bollywood presence in South Korea and South Korea's

K-Pop, K-dramas and K-beauty products in India have significantly shaped the cultural connections between the two nations. It is quite interesting to note that when a member of the BTS group opened up about '3 Idiots', his favourite Bollywood movie, it became a buzz among Indian BTS fans. Similarly, other Indian movies, for example, RRR and its Oscar-winning 'Naatu Naatu song', Taare Zameen par, My Name Is Khan, and Dangal, are quite appreciated by the Koreans. Similarly, Korean bands like BTS and Blackpink are quite popular in India. In 2021, BTS became the most-tweeted-about music band in India (News18, 2021). Various K-Pop fan clubs in India follow their idols' day-to-day activities. Indian food is quite popular in South Korea, and many vloggers and YouTubers are helping people learn about South Korean culture and vice versa.

One of the most significant steps of the Korean government to spread the Korean wave in India was the establishment of the Korean Culture Centre India in 2012. It has been playing a significant role in building connections by organising exhibitions on Korean culture and promoting the Korean language through Korean language courses in India. In 2012, KCCI organised the first K-Pop festival in India, with only 37 participants and 300 students, at a small auditorium at Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU) (Gogoi, 2017). In 2014, DD Bharati collaborated with KCCI. She began broadcasting the Hindi-dubbed serial "Dr Hur Jun Ki Sachi Dastan" to increase awareness of South Korea in India and promote cultural exchanges between the two countries (Batra, 2014).

5. Economic Implications of Cultural Connections

The growing cultural proximity between South Korea and India has significant economic implications. It fosters trade, investments and tourism between the two countries. Cultural proximity and people-to-people connections have significantly shaped consumer behaviour in India. The Korean Wave (hallyu) has increased demand for Korean products in India; for example, Korean cosmetics, Korean food, and Korean fashionable clothes have seen a steep rise in demand (Singh, 2022). In the same way, Korean conglomerates like Samsung, Hyundai, and LG have leveraged their cultural appeal to strengthen brand loyalty in India. Similarly, Indian products such as spices and Bollywood movies have found greater acceptance among Koreans.

Cultural connections between the two countries have positively shaped the tourism growth. Indian tourists are fascinated by Korea's vibrant entertainment industry and cultural festivals, while South Korean tourists travel to India for its historical Buddhist sites, Yoga, and philosophical knowledge. This exchange has boosted the revenue of both countries through hospitality and services provided. Increased tourism between the two countries creates many economic opportunities for Indians and Koreans alike. The Korean language expert has the opportunity to engage economically with Korean tourists through guiding and interpretation, and the same is true for South Korea as well. The popularity of K-Pop and K-dramas in India has

encouraged local brands to collaborate with Korean celebrities, which has fueled cross-border marketing initiatives. Recently, Sara Tendulkar became the brand ambassador of a top-rated Korean beauty brand, Laneige, and K-Pop's one of the biggest stars, Jungkook, expressed his love for chicken Makhani and Naan (Times of India, 2024). These collaborations are hugely appreciated for cross-border marketing to flourish. Similarly, South Korean companies are tapping India's huge entertainment market for joint ventures and collaborations, for example, in web series and film productions. Education and the workforce are another dimension where both countries may engage economically. Korean language programs in India and Indian IT professionals in South Korea are highly valued, demonstrating the synergy between cultural and economic ties.

6. Challenges in the Bilateral Ties

India and South Korea have shared strong cultural and economic relations for centuries. India and South Korea are, respectively, the second and sixth largest economies in Asia, with significant trade ties dating back to the historic past (Sahoo & Miglani, etc., 2023). However, the trade imbalance between the countries remains a significant challenge, with South Korea exporting more to India than it imports from India. Despite the implementation of agreements such as the Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (CEPA) in 2010, the trade deficit between India and Korea has persisted. The increasing trade deficit with South Korea has long been a key concern for India, which has more than doubled since 2009-10 (Sahoo & Miglani, etc., 2023). The trade imbalance limits the economic potential of the partnership, making it difficult for India to gain equal market access for its products in South Korea.

Additionally, despite both countries growing as cultural capitals and sharing many things in common, the awareness and acceptance of Indian culture in the South remains low. Korean popular culture, through the Korean wave, has gained immense popularity in India, but the reverse is not as pronounced in Korea. Indian cultural understanding in Korea has not penetrated to the same extent. The gap in cultural understanding of India hampers the future trajectory of the bilateral ties. The informal connections between people of both countries play a significant role in shaping cooperation and further strengthen the relationship. For example, food habits, language, and how they meet informally significantly establish bonds among people. Koreans have a prevalent 소주 culture when they meet informally for dinner, but many Indians don't have it; for some Indians, drinking wine or whisky isn't as normal as it is for Koreans. The food habits of Indians are quite different from those of Koreans; for example, vegetarianism is quite popular in some parts of India, but there is no such culture in South Korea. Therefore, there are a few cultural impediments that are crucial to a healthy relationship between the two countries. Informal connections among people play a significant role in establishing a strong relationship between two countries.

7. Conclusion

India and South Korea share strong cultural and economic ties. In recent years, the relationship between the two nations has seen a rising trend in both the economy and culture. However, the improvement in relations between India and South Korea has not fully realised its potential. The gap in fully realising the potential of the India-South Korea relationship could be attributed to informal connections, habits, and attitudes among the people. Informal connections contribute significantly to the establishment of formal connections between the two nations. Both countries emerged as cultural capitals in their own ways, and they appear complementary rather than competitive. Although India and South Korea recognise and respect each other's cultural richness and soft power, there are a few cultural differences that may become hurdles to a healthy relationship between the two countries. Despite shared cultural heritage and historical linkages, people-to-people connections may become a significant player in reshaping the future trajectory of formal ties between the two countries. Therefore, the country's cultural and soft power has emerged as an important player in reshaping its hard power.

References

- Ahuja, S.K. (2019a, April 4). Koreans maximum traveling community in the world, but skip India. Asian Community News Network.
- Batra, A. (2014, January 6). Korean serial Dr. Hur Jun Ki Sachi Dastaan coming to India. Times of India. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/tv/news/hindi/Korean-serial-Dr-Hur-Jun-Ki-Sachi-Dastaan-coming-to-India/articleshow/28477314.cms>
- Bae, Y., & Lee, Y. W. (2020). Socialized soft power: Recasting analytical path and public diplomacy. *Journal of International Relations and Development*, 23, 871-898.
- Brewster, D. (2010). India's developing relationship with South Korea: A useful friend in East Asia. *Asian Survey*, 50(2), 402-425.
- Chang, P. L., & Lee, H. (2017). The Korean wave: determinants and its implications on trade. *J Int Econ*, 84, 207-220.
- Eliküçük Yıldırım, N., & Aslan, M. (2020). China's charm defensive: Image protection by acquiring mass entertainment. *Pacific Focus*, 35(1), 141-171.
- Gogoi, M. (2017). K-drama to K-pop: Is India finally warming up to the Korean Wave?. *Hindustan Times*, 25.
- Hwang, I. (2023). Korea's soft power is driving the youth to learn Korean. *Times Study Abroad*. (Retrieved March 26, 2025) <https://india.korean-culture.org/en/1272/board/934/read/121864#:~:text=>
- Kanozia, R., & Ganghariya, G. (2021). Cultural proximity and hybridity: Popularity of Korean pop culture in India. *Media Asia*, 48(3), 219-228.
- Kim, Y., & Kwon, S. Y. (2025). 'Keeping up with the Korean Yeojas': the paradox of Korean women's participation of aesthetic exercise in contemporary Korea. *Sport in Society*, 28(1), 41-56.

- Keel, H. S. (1978). Buddhism and political power in Korean history. *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies*, 9-24.
- Kelley, C. (2019). BTS lead the growth of Hallyu to nearly 90 million fans worldwide in 2018. *Forbes*.
- Kugiel, P. (2017). *India's soft power: A new foreign policy strategy*. Routledge.
- Mazumdar, A. (2018). India's soft power diplomacy under the Modi administration: Buddhism, diaspora and yoga. *Asian Affairs*, 49(3), 468-491.
- Mishra, S. K. (2023). Soft Power in India-South Korea Relations and Role of Cultural and Popular Connections. *Journal of Indian & Asian Studies*, 4(2).
- Panda, R. (2012). India and South Korea relations: Past and future trends. *Portuguese Journal of International Affairs*, 6, 64-76.
- Sen, T. (Ed.). (2014). *Buddhism Across Asia: Networks of Material, Intellectual and Cultural Exchange*, volume 1 (Vol. 19). Institute of Southeast Asian Studies.
- Singh, S. (2022). The rise of Korean wave in India and its influence on consumer behaviour and the consumer products industry. Available at SSRN 4365651.
- Yoon, S. (2014). Cultural Identity and Korean Historical Television Dramas. *The Global Impact of South Korean Popular Culture: Hallyu Unbound*, 7-17.